

Title:

Association of echocardiographic radiomics-based features with cardiotoxicity effect in breast cancer patients from the CARDIOCARE project

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Manuscript:

The manuscript explores the association between echocardiographic radiomics-based features and cardiotoxicity in breast cancer patients from the CARDIOCARE project. Improvements in breast cancer therapy have led to increased survival, but also more cardiotoxic effects like cardiomyopathy and heart failure. The study aims to leverage radiomics analysis for non-invasive echocardiography biomarkers associated with cardiotoxicity. In a prospective cohort of 28 patients (above 60 years old, 10 developed cardiotoxicity) undergoing antineoplastic therapy, over 1500 imaging features were extracted from echocardiographic images (apical 4- and 2-chamber views) at baseline and after 3 months using a pre-trained neural network for segmentation. Cardiotoxicity was assessed by combining imaging (LVEF, GLS) and blood markers (Troponin I, Nt-pro-Bnp). Univariate analysis showed 40 textural radiomics features (mostly from the myocardium, especially in the 4-chamber end-diastolic view and 2-chamber end-systolic view) were significantly associated with cardiotoxicity, while histogram and shape features were not. The study concludes that myocardial heterogeneity quantified by radiomics could have diagnostic value for early detection of cardiac toxicity.